

THE ROLE OF INVESTMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN NAMANGAN REGION ON THE SUBJECT THESIS

Abdumutalliyev Abdulaxad Abdusamad o'g'li

Assistant of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology

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Abstract : This in our article in Namangan region investment potential development ways and measures about data given .

Key words: small business, investment , external, entrepreneurship , project , regional, construction materials .

Uzbekistan Republic Investments and external trade Ministry by in Namangan region investment activities strengthen according to complex affairs done increased Implemented affairs two main direction separated : mutual cooperation principles based on entrepreneurship and household to develop directed projects and the region complex within the development program done being increased projects .

first direction common worth 2.2 trillion to soum equal to that 's it including international finance 103 million dollars funds of institutions attraction to do at the expense of household 157 new in the direction projects done is increased and that's it through knitting , crafts , greenhouse farms , fruit and vegetable farming , animal husbandry , poultry farming , beekeeping , horticulture , jewelry , goat breeding , woodworking such as 18.4 thousand in directions person population the work with is provided .

Highlight this is necessary projects work on the way out economic of development growth points - " drivers". determination the way with region of possibilities maximum level use in order to region and district cities strong and weak sides studied .

such " drivers" in the province one textile industry is his _technological development level external in the market buyer was high good quality ready products work release enable is giving Leader foreign brands under ready clothes are yesterday work release for foreign brands with connections installation through for export for sale textile of products addition value to increase separately accent given - in the region rope again work level by 95 % increase planned . In the future internal brands Create and them external to markets before push measures on _ complex done is increased .

Also close _ in the future textile in the industry work release and export size increase planned of this _ for the first stage Toragorgon in the district specialized

textile trade and industry zone organize reach for 100 hectares land area is separated .

Goat breeding Namangan region Pop and Quiet districts historically developed account received without , this the field is also sharp activated - goat the fur again work and ready wool products work release according to industry clusters organize to do directed one series investment projects done It is planned to increase. 81 mln 128 dollar investment the project done increase traditional from gardening intensive to gardening to pass directed is from here of use economic efficiency significant level increases and in the region fruits cultivation expenses reduces Total in 2020-2021 in Namangan region all investment programs done increase and economic of development above note " drivers" . to work put through common worth 13.1 trillion 2148 projects worth soums done increased from 55 thousand more than new the work place is created .

Summary in place that's it we say maybe an investment attraction any made field without development won't stay Local and foreign investments wide attraction to do for in Namangan region investment environment more improve and attractiveness increase , this through field and of regions economy our promotion can

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